

TEACHERS WITH UNIQUE CHALLENGES VIS-À-VIS THEIR TEACHING COMPETENCE: IMPLICATIONS TO SUPPORTIVE WORK ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: This study delved into the lived experiences of teachers with unique challenges regarding their teaching competence. These challenges included personal problems, financial issues, family and caregiving responsibilities, societal expectations, and workload demands that often make them feel unseen, unheard, and less valued. The participants of the study were composed of ten (10) teachers at the Department of Education, SDO Nueva Ecija, General Tinio District. Purposive sampling was utilized. A qualitative method using a case study approach was employed to capture deeply the lived experiences of teachers with unique challenges and how they affect their teaching competence. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data. The findings of the study revealed that systemic problems, physical health burden, relationship burden, and financial burdens, showing resilience despite hardships, and the emotional impact on well-being were the themes of teachers' unique challenges. In light of their teaching competence, most teachers revealed strength, resilience, and adaptability in their teaching. They find themselves still competent. They effectively manage their situations, using strategies like compartmentalization, time management, and prioritization. On the other hand, personal health issues or intense family obligations are the major factors their perceived teaching competence can be negatively impacted. Teachers need a supportive work environment to ensure their well-being and enhance their effectiveness. This includes an atmosphere of understanding, inclusiveness, and empathy in school. Additionally, the study suggests implementing mental health programs for teachers, mentorship initiatives, financial management programs and seminars, creating a conducive school environment with adequate facilities, and strengthening leave policies for special cases.

Keywords: teachers' unique challenges, teaching competence, supportive work environment, resilience, emotional labor, systemic problems, physical health burden, relationship burden, and financial burdens.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers are like beacons; they are the ones who illuminate students' knowledge and learning path. They impart passionate knowledge, with smiling faces and unwavering dedication. They are full of life and energy, making every learning experience meaningful and enjoyable.

More than just a dispenser of knowledge and a facilitator of learning, educators fill many roles. They act as second parents, providing care, guidance, and support to their students. And just like parents, they nurture, encourage, and discipline, helping students grow academically, emotionally, and morally. Teachers also act as motivators, inspiring students to reach their full potential and empowering them to dream big and achieve their goals.

Beyond classroom teaching responsibilities, they are also counsellors, providing help and encouragement to struggling students, whether academically or personally. Aside from this, they frequently act as emergency nurses, providing care for students' sickness and minor injuries due to their clumsiness. They also serve as mediators, stepping in to resolve unexpected conflicts that arise among students. And during back-to-school Brigada Eskwela, teachers occasionally work as janitors, painters, and carpenters- going above and beyond their primary responsibilities to improve their pupils' learning environments. They clean classrooms, decorate bulletin boards, repair broken chairs, and even paint walls to make the school a conducive place for learning.

Teachers have a big heart for the students. They do home visits when students are no longer attending class. When there are school projects that some students can't afford, teachers come to the rescue. They willingly provide materials and resources to ensure no student is left behind. Sometimes, they even give money out of their own pockets to ensure students have "baon" just to attend class.

All for the welfare of the students, teachers often go the extra mile. They extend their care to make sure every child has an equal opportunity to learn and participate. Their compassion, kindness, and dedication reveal that teaching is a vocation, not just a profession to serve others.

People do honor their hard work, commitment, and the huge difference they make in the lives of future generations. However, beneath their smiles, passion, and enthusiasm in their work, a cheerful facade can mask a hidden struggle.

Teaching is indeed a fulfilling job; however, we can't deny the fact that it's really a stressful job. Studies consistently show that teachers report high levels of stress and burnout (Agyapong et al. 2022) because teachers certainly experience different challenges that go beyond the typical job stress.

Each teacher wears many hats; beyond their duty as a teacher, they also navigate a complex identity, they are also parents, siblings, sons or daughters, and more. They have diverse roles, and these roles are core to their being and even their work as professionals.

Every teacher carries a story to tell; they may be in a situation that is profoundly challenging and often misunderstood. These personal struggles can become deeply linked to their professional identity, leaving them feeling isolated and unheard. These challenges can significantly impact their well-being, and, as a result, they can even influence their competence, including how they engage and interact with the students and how they approach teaching.

Many studies within the Philippines examined the factors influencing their competence, including workload, stress, and even personal struggles. A study by Mapano et al. (2024) shows a significant relationship between workload and stress, implying that a high teaching workload correlates with increased burnout.

While there is existing research on the relationship between teacher workload and stress and how it affects teaching competence, in-depth explorations of the impact of personal identities and experiences on teaching competence that vary across contexts might be lacking. The researcher, who is also a public-school teacher, believes that, like other professionals, teachers navigate through different struggles, and these personal struggles are somehow intertwined with their professional lives. Thus, ignoring these struggles can have negative consequences for the teachers, as well as the students, and even the whole school community. Therefore, it is essential to understand first that each teacher has unique identities and experiences that they deal with than what is evident in the classroom.

Because of this, the researcher aims to gain an in-depth understanding of the teachers' different struggles in various contexts and examine how these experiences affect teachers' competence. The researcher firmly believes that this will shed light on the often-unseen struggles and challenges of teachers, and this study will raise awareness and empathy among colleagues, parents, and other community members.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Design

In order to explore various individual issues, the researcher used a Qualitative research design to conduct an in-depth understanding and holistic perspectives among the different struggles that teachers deal with in their lives.

This design fits as it explores and provides deeper insights into real-world problems. (Korstjens, 2017) Qualitative research gathers participants' experiences, perceptions, and behavior.

The researcher administered a case study to ensure the credibility and comparability of findings across cases.

Specifically, the study answered the following problems:

1. How may the profile of the teachers be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 civil status;
 - 1.4 years of experience (length of service);
 - 1.5 subject taught; and
 - 1.6 educational attainment?
2. What are the lived experiences of the teachers anchored on their unique challenges?
3. What is the impact of these on their perceived teaching competence?
4. What implications for a supportive work environment can be drawn from the findings of the study?

B. Environment

The study focused on General Tinio District, Schools Division Office of Nueva Ecija. The researcher, who is from this town, believes that by concentrating on the district, the study aims to find localized context factors that might affect teachers' competence, and this helps create policy suggestions that meet the needs of the teachers and the school system. This localized approach also makes it easier to collect data, which lets the research questions be investigated in more depth. Furthermore, this study focused only on General Tinio District, Schools Division Office of Nueva Ecija, and its findings did not broadly represent the experiences of all teachers in similar situations.

C. Respondents

The primary goal of this research was to select cases that represent distinctly different types of significant challenges that are linked to teachers' identities that are likely to impact teaching. The researcher used a purposive sampling technique, wherein the participants were purposively chosen based on their criteria provided by the researcher and on their willingness to participate in the study. An inclusive selection of cases to embody different challenges, like Personal and Family Burdens, Health and Physical Challenges, Identity and Inclusion, and Professional Status.

These criteria vary as: Breadwinner teacher, LGBT teacher, Former OFW now Teaching, Indigenous People Teacher in the Mountains, Solo Parent teacher, Multiple role or Multiple designation or overworked teacher, Teacher having a Child with Special Need, Non-tenured/ MLSB Teacher, Teacher with different side hustles, and Kidney Transplant/Dialysis Patient Teacher. These respondents were defined as teachers with unique challenges in a way that their struggles and challenges are often unseen and unheard and sometimes not acknowledged as impacting their well-being and professional duties.

D. Instrument

Data was gathered through semi-structured interviews to elicit narratives about teachers' personal experiences.

The researcher developed an interview guide questionnaire. This guide included open-ended questions to gather detailed narratives about teachers' experiences linked to their challenges, and how it impacts their perceived teaching competence. The researcher consulted with her adviser and relevant experts in the field of Education and Guidance and Counseling to enhance and validate her instrument.

The research questionnaire was divided into two parts:

Part I.

The profile of the respondents. This includes:

Demographics and professional background (age, gender, civil status, years of experience (length of service), and subject(s) taught, and educational attainment

Part II.

Lived experiences of teachers that are anchored on their challenges and their impact on their perceived competence

E. Data Analysis Plan

The data analysis followed the concepts of thematic analysis, which involve identifying, studying, and documenting patterns (themes) within the data. This method allows for interactive engagement with the data, enabling themes related to their personal challenges to arise naturally.

After the in-depth interviews, the researcher first transcribed the audio recordings into text, then systematically coded this text to identify keywords and ideas related to teachers' experiences and challenges affecting their competence. These codes were grouped into broader categories, leading to the interpretation and identification of themes that capture the essence of their lived realities and experiences. Then, analysis and interpretation were done with the individual stories to gain insight into their perspectives and how they interpret their experiences. The final stage involved interpretation, utilizing specific narratives to draw broader conclusions and implications for a supportive work environment. The researcher connected the findings back to existing literature on teachers lived experiences, challenges, and teaching competence.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Profile of the Respondents

Age. The respondents ranged in age from 28 to 59 years. The youngest were 28 and 29 years old, indicating recent entry into the teaching profession. Most teachers were in their mid-thirties to early forties, with specific ages reported as 34, 39, and 43. A significant number were in their late forties and early fifties, including respondents aged 47 and 53. The most senior participant was 59 years old.

Civil Status. Among the ten teachers, the majority were single, followed by married individuals, with one respondent identified as a widow.

Teaching Experience. Teaching experience varied widely, ranging from a newly hired teacher with only 2 years of service to a veteran with 36 years of experience. A significant portion of the respondents had been teaching for 5 to 15 years. Notably, one teacher had 25 years of teaching experience.

Subjects Taught. English was the most commonly taught subject, handled by 30% of the respondents. MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) was also a significant area, taught by 20%. At the elementary level, 20% of the teachers handled multiple subjects, including Science, Math, Filipino, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (EsP), and English. In the secondary level, subject specialization was more defined: 10% of the respondents taught TLE (Technology and Livelihood Education), while 20% focused on business-related subjects such as Fundamentals of ABM (Accountancy, Business, and Management) and Business Math under the Senior High School program.

Educational Background. All respondents (100%) held a bachelor's degree. Common specializations included Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) in MAPEH, Science, and English, as well as Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd). Additionally, 20% of the teachers had earned additional bachelor's degrees in fields such as Accountancy and Real Estate Management. A notable portion—50%—had either completed or were currently pursuing master's degrees or graduate-level coursework.

B. Lived Experiences of Teachers with Unique Challenges

Systemic Challenges

Based on the findings, systemic problems were highlighted through the teachers' lived experiences.

The IP teacher described the poor infrastructure in geographically isolated areas, including poor roads, inadequate classrooms and resources, and a complete absence of internet communication. These conditions cause them to sacrifice and suffer.

The Multiple Designation or Overworked Teacher juggled many responsibilities, serving as everything from a teacher, guidance counselor, EsP Coordinator, canteen manager, and even unofficial nurse—all without extra compensation. As a result, she finds herself burdened.

The Non-Tenured MLSB teacher pointed out that although she is not yet permanent, the burden has resulted in overloaded responsibilities, with the work unfairly falling on her because she is new, younger, and single. This teacher is often overworked because of her perceived availability and eagerness to help. She accepted all the workload in pursuit of a permanent position. She also shared her difficult experience handling a class with different attitudes.

The theme is also evident in the Former OFW teacher's experience of being new to the system, as she faced culture shock and a lack of mentorship. This is further supported by a study of Frianeza et al. (2024), which found that these challenges within the education system significantly affect teachers' instructional strategies and methods, as well as their efforts toward professional growth. These challenges affect teachers' instructional strategies and professional growth, as they struggle with low salaries and insufficient support for continuous development. As supported by Cahilog et al. (2023), there are challenges within the system that push teachers to consider opportunities to work abroad. These challenges include overwhelming workloads and limited compensation, geographical and infrastructure issues, financial strain, administrative and bureaucratic burdens, student-related pressures, and even insufficient health benefits.

Physical Health, Relationships, and Financial Burdens

The data demonstrated that many teachers are consistently weighed down by physical health, relationships, and financial burdens. These problems are interconnected, describing both physical health and financial burdens simultaneously, or relationship and financial burdens at the same time.

The physical health struggle is evident in the Kidney Transplant and Dialysis Patient Teacher, who manages the demanding routine of peritoneal dialysis (PD) four times daily while simultaneously handling her teaching responsibilities. She has to endure fatigue, travel costs, and occasional medical expenses.

Regarding financial burdens, this is evident in the Breadwinner Teacher, who shoulders the entire financial responsibility of her extended family, causing her to fall into personal debt. Adding to her burdens are physical health problems, as she was hospitalized and, being single, solely responsible for all medical expenses.

Moreover, the Teacher with Multiple Side Hustles showed that despite a decent salary in a government teaching position, it often does not provide enough financial security for future investments or comfortable family support. Being a solo parent motivates many to find other ways to earn money.

Lastly, with regard to relationship burdens, this was manifested in the lived experiences of a Solo Parent Teacher balancing her professional duties with the full responsibility of raising her children. This demanding situation leads to constantly making tough sacrifices between her child and work obligations.

These challenges weigh heavily on their physical, relational, and financial responsibilities. In their situations, challenges are intertwined. For parent-teachers, parenting responsibilities can often clash with their professional duties. This, coupled with financial obligations and the difficulty of managing physical health, creates stress. The teacher with a chronic illness also faced a daily battle, meticulously managing her treatment and struggling with the financial burden of obtaining all her medicines from the city.

Research by Tagapulot et al. (2024) validated this, revealing that several significant financial challenges encountered by public school teachers stem from a combination of personal needs, family responsibilities, and systemic issues related to their profession.

Resilience Despite Hardships

Despite these challenges, a deep sense of resilience and dedication emerged.

The Former OFW Teacher's journey back to the Philippine education system, marked by initial culture shock and a complete lack of mentorship, showcases her extraordinary adaptability, honed by her varied career abroad.

The IP Teacher in the mountains experienced systemic neglect, such as logistical challenges, inadequate infrastructure, lack of resources, and issues concerning student well-being. Still, she continues teaching with the resources at hand and dedicates her life to teaching the Dumagat community in the mountains.

Similarly, the journey of the LGBT Teacher to self-acceptance and his commitment to openly discussing gender equality with students demonstrates a different kind of resilience. This fosters understanding and inclusiveness within the school environment, despite his past negative experiences and false accusations.

Resiliency is also evident in the teacher with a kidney transplant, who, despite performing dialysis multiple times a day, continues to teach, relying on meticulous self-management and the support of her students and colleagues.

Go et al. (2020) revealed that Filipino teachers demonstrate a high ability to compartmentalize personal problems, which positively correlates with their teaching performance.

The Emotional Impact on Well-being

The study revealed that, based on the lived experiences of teachers, emotions have either a positive or negative effect on their well-being.

This is evident in the teacher who has a child with special needs; she showed deep empathy for her struggling students because she understood their difficulties firsthand.

The Breadwinner Teacher, being the sole provider for her family and burdened by debt, experienced emotional isolation, finding that the school served as her comfort zone and a place where she could temporarily escape her worries when stressed.

The Solo Parent Teacher experienced stress from dealing with difficult choices—whether to fully support her child or prioritize her professional duties.

The Multiple Designation/Overworked Teacher carried an emotional burden, admitting she was neglecting her family due to job demands. She also shared her experience of being physically present but mentally absent because of exhaustion from being overworked.

The MLSB Teacher's feelings of sadness and burden, as well as uncertainty about her career choice due to her demanding tasks, further illustrated emotional strain. Similarly, the Former OFW Teacher, lacking proper guidance, is contemplating changing careers once more.

These emotional impacts were highlighted in the given situations of teachers, where their emotions directly influenced their actions and well-being.

An article from Psychologs World mentioned that when teachers are constantly stressed and tired, their ability to engage with students, be emotionally present, and teach effectively all suffer. On the other hand, a study by Belarmino et al. (2018) showed that teachers with high emotional intelligence can effectively regulate their emotions, allowing them to cope with various stressors and adversities. This ability to manage their feelings also prepares them to handle future challenges.

A study by Panela et al. (2021) concluded that many teachers face considerable difficulty in balancing their responsibilities both within and outside the school environment. A common outcome for these teachers is that they spend the majority of their time on school-related activities, often at the expense of their personal lives. Their personal challenges are often linked to their work.

A study by Rahmi (2024) emphasized that the mental well-being of teachers is crucial; when it is poor, it can negatively impact students' mental health and the entire educational process. It is therefore imperative to implement strategies that enhance teachers' mental health.

C. Impact on Perceived Teaching Competence

According to the findings, the perceived teaching competence of teachers generally has a positive impact. However, some situations show significant negative effects on their perceived teaching competence. These issues impacted various aspects of teaching, including how teachers planned lessons, taught their classes, managed classrooms, interacted with students, and engaged in professional development.

The influence of teachers who are breadwinners, LGBTQ+ individuals, former Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs), teachers of Indigenous Peoples (IPs), those with multiple roles, teachers with a child with special needs, non-tenured MLSB teachers, and those with different side hustles is primarily positive. By drawing on their unique identities and life experiences, these teachers turn their challenges into powerful strengths.

For the breadwinner teacher, the demands extend far beyond the classroom, often carrying significant personal and financial burdens. Yet, she demonstrated remarkable resilience by consciously compartmentalizing these struggles, so they do not affect her work. The same is true for the teacher with different side hustles and the teacher with a child with special needs. They separate work from personal problems to stay focused on their responsibilities.

Similarly, the LGBTQ+ teacher transforms his identity into a source of strength, infusing cheerfulness and humor into his lessons. The former OFW draws from her experiences abroad to manage her classroom effectively and navigate school tasks with confidence. Even the teacher of Indigenous Peoples in the mountains, despite the lack of resources and support, felt she proved her competence by adapting her teaching to focus on fundamental skills.

The multirole teacher, who simultaneously manages responsibilities as a classroom teacher, guidance counselor, and canteen manager, demonstrates emotional labor. Despite her exhaustion from these multiple roles, she consistently practices emotional regulation and surface acting—presenting herself as energetic and lively before her students even when she is tired. This is supported by Tsang et al. (2021), who found that teachers frequently use emotional labor strategies, such as surface acting (faking emotions) and deep acting (genuinely trying to feel the emotion). While, the non-tenured/MLSB teacher embraced challenges as opportunities for growth.

Teachers juggling multiple roles, teachers with a child with special needs, and those with multiple side hustles also affirmed their competence through effective time management and prioritization. Their ability to skillfully manage various challenges while still fulfilling their professional duties highlights their dedication to providing quality education.

On the other hand, the solo parent and the kidney transplant patient experienced a negative impact. The solo parent's frequent absences due to the demands of solo parenting made it difficult for her to be consistently present at work, leading to diminished confidence in her professional capability. Her personal experiences also affected her ability to grasp certain lessons. For the kidney transplant patient, her physical limitations, frequent medical appointments, and missed professional development opportunities contributed to reduced perceived competence. These factors limit her energy, availability, and access to essential training, which hinders her growth.

The majority of the teachers demonstrated strength, resilience, and adaptability in teaching. This is viewed as a positive impact, as they consistently manage their circumstances or employ strategies such as effective time management and prioritization. Their capacity to compartmentalize personal struggles and transform challenges into strengths illustrates resilience and dedication. However, perceived teaching competence is negatively affected when personal health issues or intense family obligations are involved.

As stated by Go et al. in their studies, Filipino teachers show a strong capacity to compartmentalize their difficulties and demonstrate the ability to perceive, understand, manage, and utilize their emotions. This enables them to maintain a positive disposition and deliver high-quality classroom performance, regardless of personal issues. Similarly, Peixoto et al. (2018) stated that teacher resilience offers a valuable lens through which to understand why educators persevere despite the challenges of their profession. It is more than just bouncing back from difficulties—it involves maintaining balance, staying dedicated, and actively confronting the inevitable challenges that come with teaching. This is what makes them successful.

D. Implications for a Supportive Work Environment

The lived experiences of teachers with unique identities demonstrate the need for a supportive work environment.

Based on the findings, it is implied that when teachers feel supported, their psychological well-being improves. This is evident in the LGBT teacher's journey of self-acceptance, which was fostered through supportive relationships with colleagues and open discussions with students.

Additionally, the emotional burdens faced by the breadwinner teacher's isolation and the overworked teacher's exhaustion—along with her admitted neglect of family responsibilities—highlight the toll that a lack of support can take on a teacher's mental and emotional health. Mental health programs and inclusive training for teachers are recommended to alleviate immense stress and emotional burdens. These initiatives can foster a sense of belonging and value, rather than anxiety and burnout.

The evidence clearly suggests that when teachers are not battling systemic deficiencies and overwhelming workloads, they can dedicate more time and energy to lesson planning, classroom management, and the design of creative teaching methods. This, in turn, helps students learn more effectively.

The overworked teacher's struggle to manage time due to multiple designations, which hinders her ability to complete Daily Lesson Logs, directly impacts her performance in the classroom. Similarly, the MLSB non-tenured teacher—although flexible—felt overwhelmed by excessive demands. These issues indicate the need for improved workload distribution policies to empower teachers to focus on their core role: educating students.

Moreover, despite their struggles, the recognition received by the non-tenured MLSB teacher and the overworked teacher inspired and motivated them to continue teaching. A supportive workplace, characterized by recognition, encourages teachers to stay motivated and committed.

Family and physical health challenges are indeed difficult to navigate. For solo parent teachers, those with children with special needs, or teachers managing chronic health conditions, schools should provide flexible arrangements or accommodations such as modified schedules and enhanced special leave privileges. A truly supportive environment is one that is understanding and responsive to the diverse needs of its teachers. This is exemplified by the relief felt by the kidney transplant patient, who reported feeling unburdened in the presence of supportive students and colleagues.

For the non-tenured MLSB teacher who considered changing careers due to her experiences, and for the former OFW teacher who nearly resigned because of the lack of guidance and assistance, the implications point to the damaging effects of unsupportive environments on teacher retention. When teachers feel overworked or unsupported, they are more likely to seek employment elsewhere. This underscores the need for improved induction programs and mentoring systems. In particular, new teachers should benefit from a lighter workload during their initial years, giving them time to adapt to their new roles.

For the IP teacher, although she managed to continue teaching, she was limited to basic numeracy and literacy due to the lack of resources and the specific needs of the learners. This suggests that students in these settings are at risk of missing a more comprehensive educational experience. Thus, there is a pressing need for full government support—from school-level assistance to community development in Indigenous Peoples' areas. Tangible resources, improved infrastructure, fully supported feeding programs, and other systemic solutions are needed to ease the burdens on teachers in geographically isolated communities.

In conclusion, a supportive work environment is the foundation for both effective teaching and teacher well-being. When a teacher's well-being is compromised, student learning is directly affected. A genuinely supportive work environment helps reduce stress and emotional burdens, allowing teachers to thrive personally and professionally.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

1. Based on the teacher's profile and experiences, personal identities and circumstances are deeply intertwined with their professional lives; their unique challenges, both consciously and unconsciously, impact a distinct aspect of the teaching and learning process.
2. The prevalent issues are systemic challenges and the often unseen and unspoken physical health, relationships, and financial burdens. Despite the challenges, the teachers view themselves still as effective and competent teachers as they display resilience, adaptability, professionalism, flexibility, and commitment to their work. Signifying the teacher's ability to navigate personal challenges and sustain or even elevate their teaching competence. Meanwhile, challenges related to family and health have a significant negative impact on their perceived competence.
3. The learners will always be the ones to suffer if the well-being of the teacher is compromised. In connection with this, teachers' well-being can be an important factor in effective learning outcomes; therefore, the elevation and prioritization of teachers' well-being are crucial.
4. Teachers are in crucial need of a supportive work environment. Mental health programs, mentorship, financial management programs, a conducive school environment with adequate facilities, and administrative support programs were suggested.

B. Recommendations

1. School administrators should foster a culture of empathy, understanding, and inclusivity. Understanding the diverse backgrounds and experiences of teachers requires more consideration from the school head. Especially for new in-service and seasoned teachers, teachers of every gender identity, teachers struggling with chronic health issues, solo-parent teachers, teachers who work side jobs to support their families, and teachers who have transitioned to teaching careers.
2. The Department of Education should consider the following:
 - A. Strengthening the collaboration with the local government unit to prioritize remote schools by allocating specific budgets and resources for infrastructure development, such as classrooms and communication lines, in geographically isolated areas.
 - B. Providing mentorship programs and induction programs for new teachers, career shifters into teaching, and even Non-Education Graduates taking Professional Education Units.
 - C. Organizing financial literacy and debt management programs can be organized, focusing on budgeting, debt management planning, and wise investment strategies for teachers.

D. School administrators may conduct a comprehensive review of non-teaching duties assigned to teachers, especially in smaller and remote schools. They should optimize workload by relocating administrative tasks and considering hiring more support staff to ease the burden on multiple designated roles of teachers. Additionally, MLSB teachers should not be overburdened with responsibilities that are unjust to their compensation and the support they receive.

E. Organizing Gender and Development Sensitivity training in Schools for students and teachers to foster inclusivity and a deeper understanding of teachers with different gender identities.

3. The government may implement policies that offer flexible schedules, reasonable workloads, and specialized support to assist exceptional cases of teachers, such as solo parents and those living with chronic health conditions, thereby minimizing a negative impact on the teaching and learning process. They may also provide readily available resources that can save time, such as pre-made lesson plans. Furthermore, foster a strong support system where colleagues can cover a class or share resources in teaching.

4. School should establish a supportive environment where mental and physical health needs are acknowledged and respected. The school guidance program for teachers should be strengthened. Mental health support services for teachers should be made available, including access to counseling, stress management programs, and workshops. Additionally, the Department of Education may create sick leave policies that encourage rest and recovery, as well as policies for Mental health support and leave for Teachers to support their well-being.

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